

Synthesis of 1-Substituted-5-carboxy-4,6-dimethyl-2(1H)-pyridones

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A number of 1-substituted-5-carboxy-4,6-dimethyl-2(1H)-pyridones have been synthesised by the condensation of 4,6-dimethyl-5-carboxy-2-oxo-(2H)-pyran with substituted-hydrazines. Their structural assignments are based on elemental analyses, ir and nmr spectral data.

THE reaction of 4,6-dimethyl-5-carboxy-2-oxo-(2H)-pyran with substituted-hydrazines is described in this communication. The reaction involves replacement of ring oxygen of 4,6-dimethyl-5-carboxy-2-oxo-(2H)-pyran by nitrogen to give 1-substituted-5-carboxy-4,6-dimethyl-2(1H)-pyridones (1) (Table 1). The carbonyl group at position-2 of 4,6-dimethyl-5-carboxy-(2H)-pyran is lactonic carbonyl and does not react with the substituted-hydrazines¹. The structural assignments of 1 were based on elemental analyses, ir and nmr spectral data. The ir spectra of 1 showed peaks around 3 210 (OH), 1 712 (lactonic C=O) and 820 cm⁻¹ (substituted-phenyl).

Experimental

General procedure : 4,6-Dimethyl-5-carboxy-2-oxo-(2H)-pyran (0.01 mol) and substituted-hydrazine (0.01 mol) were refluxed in a mixture of ethanol (2 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) for 5 h. The product that separated on cooling was recrystallised from acetic acid—ethanol to give 1.

In the case of semicarbazide hydrochloride, the reaction was carried out in ethanol—glacial acetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate for 3 h. The physical data of condensation products (1) of 4,6-dimethyl-5-carboxy-2-oxo-(2H)-pyran with

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 1-SUBSTITUTED-5-CARBOXY-4,6-DIMETHYL-2(1H)-PYRIDONES

Sl. no.	R	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					O	H	N
1.	4-Nitrophenylamino	65	200	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₆ N ₂	55.30 (55.44)	4.22 (4.29)	13.19 (13.86)
2.	2,4-Dinitrophenylamino	85	190	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₄	48.21 (48.27)	3.35 (3.44)	15.01 (16.09)
3.	2-Chlorophenylamino	70	285d	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	57.89 (57.43)	4.41 (4.44)	9.48 (9.57)
4.	4-Chlorophenylamino	65	295	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	57.40 (57.43)	4.42 (4.44)	9.50 (9.57)
5.	1-Naphthylamino	82	145	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂	70.09 (70.12)	5.17 (5.19)	9.07 (9.09)
6.	2-Naphthylamino	75	199	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂	70.10 (70.12)	5.18 (5.19)	9.06 (9.09)
7.	4-Sulphonylphenylamino	68	260	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₆ N ₂ S	49.81 (49.85)	4.41 (4.45)	12.42 (12.46)
8.	4-Methoxyphenylamino	85	198d	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂	62.43 (62.50)	5.51 (5.55)	9.70 (9.72)
9.	NH ₂ CONH—	75	270	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₂	47.98 (48.00)	4.85 (4.88)	18.64 (18.66)

The nmr (CDCl₃) spectra of 1, in general, exhibited signals at δ 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.15 (1H, s, CH), 2.60 (1H, s, NH), 9.90 (1H, s, COOH).

(1)

4-nitrophenylhydrazine, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine, 2-chlorophenylhydrazine, 4-chlorophenylhydrazine, 1-naphthylhydrazine, 2-naphthylhydrazine, 4-methoxyphenylhydrazine and semicarbazide hydrochloride are given in Table 1.

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Reference

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